

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF DOLUTEGRAVIR MICROEMULSION TO IMPROVE ORAL BIOAVAILABILITY

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Article Received on 15 October 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Nov., 2025,
Article Published on 10 Nov. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17578856>

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How to cite this Article: M. Naveen Kumar^{*}, Dr. K. Jaganathan, and Dr. N. Senthil Kumar. (2025). Formulation and Characterization of Dolutegravir Microemulsion To Improve Oral Bioavailability. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(11), XXX–XXX. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research work is to Formulation and Characterization of Dolutegravir Microemulsion to Improve Oral Bioavailability for the treatment of Human Immunodeficiency Virus Type 1 (HIV-1) infection and AIDS. The present work is pre- formulation studies like organoleptic properties, solubility, compatibility studies by FTIR and calibration studies using UV spectroscopy. These studies aimed to Development of different formulations (DTR 1, 2, 3, 4) with various compositions. The studies which is involved in pre- formulation study of Microemulsion are Drug-excipient compatibility studies, Standard calibration curve of Dolutegravir and Preliminary Investigations like Screening of Oil for Microemulsion, Screening of Surfactant and Co-Surfactant and Construction of Phase Diagrams and finally by doing the studies like Thermodynamic Stability Studies, Type of Microemulsion, pH Determination, Rheological

Characterization, Transmittance Test, Drug Content Estimation, In- vitro Drug Release Studies, Globule Size and Zeta Potential Measurement to confirmed the Characterization of Dolutegravir Microemulsion. The studies revealed that there is slight reduction in the drug content and % Transmittance after storage for 6months. From the data it was indicated that

the optimized Dolutegravir Microemulsion can be stable up to 6 months. The study demonstrates that the developed Microemulsion DTR 4 formulation containing oleic acid (27%), Tween20 (28%), Ethanol (7%) and water (3%) is a transparent, less viscous system and stable system. Particle size and Zeta potential of optimized formulation were found to be 54.30nm and - 5.61Mv. The stability studies confirmed that the optimized formulation can stable up to 6 months.

KEYWORDS: Dolutegravir, Microemulsion, Characterization, FTIR, UV, Stability Studies, Pre-formulation Studies.

INTRODUCTION

A microemulsion is a system of water, oil and an amphiphile which is a single optically isotropic and thermodynamically stable liquid solution.

Microemulsions (μE) are usually in the range of 10-100 nm. These homogeneous systems, which can be prepared over a wide range of surfactant concentration and oil to water ratio, are all fluids of low viscosity.

Microemulsions as drug delivery tool show favourable properties like thermodynamic stability (long shelf-life), easy formation (zero interfacial tension and almost spontaneous formation), optical isotropy, ability to be sterilized by filtration, high surface area (high solubilization capacity) and very small droplet size. The small droplets also provide better adherence to membranes and transport drug molecules in a controlled fashion (Talegaonkar S *et al.*, 2008, Sarkhejiya naimish A *et al.*, 2010).

The components of microemulsion formation as oils and surfactants are largely present but due to their toxicity, irritancy and unclear mechanism of action retards their use. For mild microemulsions to form, biocompatible, clinically acceptable, non toxic components should be screened. Therefore greater emphasis is laid upon use of generally regarded as safe (GRAS) excipients.

In the pharmaceutical field, nonionic surfactants are widely used as they are less irritative than ionic surfactants. When the surfactant concentration exceeds a certain value, aggregates of surfactant called "micelle" are formed. The critical concentration of surfactant where micelles are formed is called critical micelle concentration (CMC).

Type of Microemulsions

- a) O/W microemulsion
- b) W/O microemulsion
- c) O/W type, W/O type and Bicontinuous microemulsion

Emulsions can be commonly classified as water-in oil (W/O) emulsion or oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion. Generally speaking, hydrophilic surfactant forms O/W emulsion easily and hydrophobic surfactant is likely to form W/O emulsion. Microemulsions have various textures such as oil droplets in water, water droplets in oil, bi continuous mixtures (Akhtar Ali et al., 2012)

Factors Affecting of Microemulsions Packing ratio

The HLB of surfactant determines the type of microemulsion through its influence on molecular packing and film curvature. The analysis of film curvature for surfactant association's leadings to the formation of microemulsion. Critical packing ratio is given by:

$$C.P.P = V / (a \times l)$$

where,

V = volume of surfactant molecule a = head group surface area

l = length

- ❖ If c.p.p is between 0-1, interface curves towards water (positive)
- ❖ If c.p.p is greater than 1, interface curves towards oil (negative)
- ❖ If c.p.p is equal to 1, then either bicontinuous or lamellar structure. Property of surfactant, oil phase and temperature

The type of microemulsion depends on the nature of surfactant. Surfactant contains hydrophilic head group and lipophilic tail group. The areas of this group, which are a measure of the differential tendency of water to swell head group and oil to swell the tail area, are important for specific formulation when estimating the surfactant HLB in a particular system.

METHODS FOR MICROEMULSION FORMULATION

Phase Titration Method

Microemulsions are prepared by the spontaneous emulsification method and can be depicted with the help of phase diagrams. Construction of phase diagram is a useful approach to study the complex series of interactions that can occur when different components are mixed.

Microemulsions are formed along with various association structures (including emulsion, micelles, lamellar, hexagonal, cubic, and various gels and oily dispersion) depending on the chemical composition and concentration of each component.

Phase inversion method

Phase inversion of microemulsions occurs upon addition of excess of the dispersed phase or in response to temperature. During phase inversion drastic physical changes occur including changes in particle size that can affect drug release both *in vivo* and *in vitro*. These methods make use of changing the spontaneous curvature of the surfactant. For non-ionic surfactants, this can be achieved by changing the temperature of the system, forcing a transition from an *o/w* microemulsion at low temperatures to a *w/o* microemulsion at higher temperatures (transitional phase inversion). During cooling, the system crosses a point of zero spontaneous curvature and minimal surface tension, promoting the formation of finely dispersed oil droplets. This method is referred to as phase inversion temperature (PIT) method.

The literature survey based on microemulsion of Dolutegravir and experimental design, Du H, Yang H *et al.*, (2008), Gulshan Chabra *et al.*, (2011), Anita Patel *et al.*, (2012), Sajal Kumar Jha *et al.*, (2011) and *etc.*

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

S. No	Materials	Grade	Manufacturer
1	Dolutegravir	IP	Drugs India, Hyderabad
2	Oleic acid	A.R	Central Drug House Pvt.Ltd, New Delhi
3	Tween 20	A.R	LOBA Chemicals Pvt Ltd, Mumbai.
4	Ethanol	A.R	Changshu Yangyuon Chemicals, China.
5	Hydrochloric acid	LR	SD Fine Chem.Ltd. Mumbai
6	Potassium chloride	A.R	RFCL Limited (Rankem), New delhi

Equipments Used

S. No	Instruments	Manufacturer
1	Electronic Balance	Essae. Goa
2	UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model UV-2600 plus)	Analytical Technologies Limited, Mumbai
3	FTIR Spectrophotometer	Thermo Nicolet, USA.
4	Magnetic stirrer	Remi equipments pvt Ltd, Mumbai.
5	Dissolution test apparatus (DS8000 Model)	Lab India, Mumbai
6	Digital pH meter	Systronics, Hyd.

7	Mechanical stirrer	Remi Electrotechnik, Vasai
8	Brookfield viscometer	Brookfield Engineering laboratories, U.S.A
9	Centrifuge	REMI Electrotechnik, Vasai.
10	Hot air oven	Kavin Scientific Products, Chennai.
11	Zeta sizer ver.6.34	Malvern instruments ltd., Vadodara.

Methodology Preformulation Study

Drug-excipient compatibility studies

Prior to the development of the dosage forms the preformulation study was carried out. IR spectral studies lies more in the qualitative identification of substances either in pure form or in combination with polymers and excipients and acts as a tool in establishment of chemical interaction. Since I.R. is related to covalent bonds, the spectra can provide detailed information about the structure of molecular compounds. In order to establish this point, comparisons were made between the spectrum of the substances and the pure compound. The above discussions imply that infrared data is helpful to confirm the identity of the drug and to detect the interaction of the drug with the carriers. FTIR spectra were recorded with a Thermo Nicolet. Japan In the range 450–4000 cm^{-1} using a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 16 scans. Samples were diluted with KBr mixing Powder, and pressed to obtain self-supporting disks.

Standard calibration curve of Dolutegravir

Calibration curve of Dolutegravir was taken in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2)

Standard Graph by using 0.1N HCl Preparation of solution Preparation of 0.1 N HCl Solution: 0.1M HCl was prepared by diluting 8.5 ml of concentrated Hydrochloric acid to 1000 ml distilled water. Preparation of standard solution: 100 mg of Dolutegravir was accurately weighed and dissolved in small quantity of methanol and make up to 100 ml volume with of 0.1 N HCl buffer solution to form 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ stock solution (SS-I). From stock solution draw 10 ml and diluted to 100ml to get concentration of 100 (SS-II) Preparation of working standard solution: $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ From SS-II aliquots of 0.5 ml, 1 ml, 1.5 ml, 2 ml, 2.5 ml, 3.0 ml, 3.5 ml, 4.0 ml, 4.5 ml, 5 ml were pipetted out into a series of 10 ml volumetric flask.

The volume was made up with 0.1N HCl to get final concentration of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ respectively. The absorbance of the resulting solution was then measured at 313 nm using UV spectrophotometer against respective parent solvent as a blank. The

standard curve was obtained by plotting absorbance V/s. concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ (Vishnu P. Choudhari *et al.*, 2011).

PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS

Screening of Oil for Microemulsion

The solubility of Dolutegravir in various oils like Castor oil, olive oil, oleic acid, Eucalyptus oil, coconut oil, Isopropyl myristate was determined by dissolving an excess amount of Dolutegravir in 5 ml of each of the selected oils in stoppered vials separately for the determination of solubility.

An excess amount of Dolutegravir was added to each stoppered vial and mixed using a vortex mixer. The mixture vials were then kept in a shaker for 72 h to get to equilibrium.

The equilibrated samples were removed from the shaker and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 30 min. The supernatant was taken and filtered through a $0.45\ \mu\text{m}$ membrane filter.

The concentration of drug was determined in each oils by UV spectrophotometer with suitable dilution with 0.1N HCL at their respective wavelength 313nm (Sajal Kumar Jha *et al.*; 2011).

Screening of Surfactant and Co-Surfactant

The criteria for the selection of surfactant were its HLB value and non- toxic nature. Several surfactants including Tween-80, Tween-20 were screened.

Co-surfactants were selected based on their capability to form stable microemulsion with relevant surfactants at a minimum concentration.

Based on this, several co-surfactants including Polyethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400) and Ethanol were screened (Sajal Kumar Jha *et al.*; 2011)

Construction of Phase Diagrams

On the basis of drug solubility in various microemulsions components, different combination of oil, water and surfactant/cosurfactant were selected.

The pseudo-ternary phase diagrams of oil, surfactant: cosurfactant, and water were developed using surfactant titration method.

The mixtures of oil and water at certain weight ratios varying from 1:9 to 9:1 were titrated

with surfactant/co-surfactant mix in a dropwisemanner.

Pseudo ternary phase diagram was achieved by titrating with four different ratios of Surfactant and Cosurfactant (1:1, 1:2.2:1, 4:1) until it turns from hazy to transparent.

The point at which the solution becomes cloudy or turbid was the end point.

Each formulation point was put on ternary graph of oil, surfactant/cosurfactant and water system. After getting end point of each formulation they joined one to other with line and completed the phase diagram.

Formulation Design

On the basis of the solubility studies, oleic acid was selected as the oil phase.

- Tween 20 and Ethanol were selected as surfactant and cosurfactant respectively.
- Distilled water was used as an aqueous phase.
- Predetermined amounts of the drug were dissolved in the required quantity of oil, surfactant and cosurfactant with varying ratios.
- Distilled water was added to the above mixture as a fixed ratio.
- Surfactant and co-surfactant were added gradually with continuous stirring, which resulted in the formulation of a transparent and homogenous microemulsion.
- Parameters optimized for the preparation of microemulsion were the type and concentration of the oil phase, surfactant and cosurfactant. (Sajal Kumar Jha et al;2011, Rohit Ramesh Shah et al., 2010)

Formulation code	Oil %	S:CoS %	Water%
DTR 1	25.5	70	4.5
DTR 2	26	70	3.9
DTR 3	26.5	70	3.3
DTR 4	27	70	3.0

Characterization of Microemulsion

Thermodynamic Stability Studies

- To overcome the problem of metastable formulation, thermodynamic stability tests were performed.
- Centrifugation technique helps to determine behaviour of small particles in gravitational field i.e., their separation rate is quite simple and inexpensive providing a rapid full-proof identification of the system as microemulsion.

- Prepared formulations were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 30 min and then examined for Phase separation (K.R. Jadhav et al., 2010).
- Those formulations that did not show any phase separation were taken for the heating and cooling cycle at temperature of 4°C and 45°C for 48 h were done. The formulations were then observed for phase separation. The formulations which were stable at these temperatures, those formulations that survived thermodynamic stability tests were selected for the further studies (Sajal Kumar Jha et al; 2011).

Type of Microemulsion

The type of microemulsion was identified by the staining method. The water-soluble dye methylene blue and the oil-soluble dye Sudan red were equally added onto the blank microemulsion and Dolutegravir loaded Microemulsion to evaluate the diffusion speed of the two dyes. If the blue dye diffuses faster than the red dye, then the type of microemulsion is o/w, and vice versa for the w/o. (Gulshan Chhabra et al., 2011)

pH Determination

The pH of the each formulation was found to be measured by a digital pH meter standardized using pH 4.0 and 7.0 standard buffers before use. (Systronics, Hyd.) (Kalra.Rupali et al, 2010, K.R. Jadhav et al., 2010).

Rheological Characterization

- The rheological studies of samples were carried out with Brookfield Digital viscometer (LV DV-E model) using S-18 spindle number.
- The developed formulations were poured into the small sample adaptor of the Brookfield viscometer and the angular velocity increased gradually from 0.5 to 100 rpm.
- The system was calibrated using Brookfield viscosity standard fluids. (Surjyanarayan Mandal et al., 2010).

Transmittance Test

- The droplets of the microemulsions being smaller than 1/4th the wavelength of visible light permit white light to pass through the dispersed system making it transparent or translucent.
- The microemulsion systems were inspected for optical transparency and homogeneity by usual observation against strong light.
- The systems were also checked for the presence of undissolved drug or other solid

ingredient. (Martin., 1990)

- Transparency of microemulsion was checked by measuring transmittance at 313 nm with 0.1N HCl as blank by using UV spectrophotometer (Vandana Patel et al., 2010).

Drug Content Estimation

Microemulsion containing 100mg drug was dissolved in 100ml 0.1N HCl taken in volumetric flask. The drug was allowed to dissolve in the solvent.

- Then the solvent was filtered, 1ml was taken in 50ml volumetric solution and diluted up to the mark with 0.1N HCl and analyzed spectrometrically at 313 nm.

In- vitro Drug Release Studies

Dolutegravir 200mg equivalent weight was filled in hard gelatin capsule shell and drug release studies was carried out for each formulation by using Dissolution test apparatus (DS8000 Model) Type II.

- Under pH condition simulative gastro intestinal tract 900 ml dissolution media was taken.
- The basket rotation was adjusted to 100 rpm, the temperature being maintained at $37\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the study.
- A buffer of pH 1.2 was used as dissolution medium for a period of 2hrs as average gastric emptying time is 2hrs.
- 5ml of sample of dissolution medium was withdrawn and replaced with fresh dissolution medium.
- The samples were analyzed for drug concentration by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 313 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Calibration Curve Data of Dolutegravir

S. No	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 313nm
1	5	0.088
2	10	0.17
3	15	0.261
4	20	0.356
5	25	0.463
6	30	0.568
7	35	0.666
8	40	0.76
9	45	0.849
10	50	0.955

Drug and excipients compatibility studies

The compatibility of drug and excipients used in the Microemulsion were characterized by FTIR spectra. The FTIR spectrum of pure.

Dolutegravir and Microemulsion formulation were almost similar because of the same functional groups. It indicates that there was no interaction between Dolutegravir and excipients used in the formulation.

FTIR Spectra of Pure Drug

IR Interpretation of Drug Dolutegravir

S.NO	Interpretation	IR absorption bands(cm^{-1})	
		Characteristic peak	Observed peak
1.	NH ₂ Stretch	3070-3350	3226.40
2.	O-H Stretch	3000-2500	3051.35
3.	C-H Stretch	2950 – 2850	2940.75
4.	C-CH ₃ Stretch	2862-2882, 2652-2972	2986.09
5.	C=O Stretch	1700-1900	1756.35

FTIR Spectra of Drug and Tween 20

Interpretation of Drug and Tween 20

S.NO	Interpretation	IR absorption bands(cm^{-1})	
		Characteristic peak	Observed peak
1.	N-H Stretch	3070-3350	3006.22
2.	O-H Stretch	3000-2500	2855.37
3.	Alkyl C-H Stretch	2950 - 2850	2926.59
4.	C-CH ₃ Stretch	2862-2882, 2652-2972	2674.64

FTIR Spectra of Mixture of Drug and Oleic

IR Interpretation of Drug and Oleic acid

S. NO	Interpretation	IR absorption bands(cm^{-1})	
		Characteristic peak	Observed peak
1.	N-H Stretch	3070-3350	3423.05
2.	O-H Stretch	3000-2500	2855.29
3.	C-H Stretch	2950 – 2850	2869.21
4.	C-CH ₃ Stretch	2862-2882, 2652-2972	1960.70
5.	C=O Stretch	1700-1900	1735.34

FTIR Spectra of Drug, Tween20 and Oleic Acid

IR Interpretation of Drug with Solvents

S.NO	Interpretation	IR absorption bands(cm^{-1})	
		Characteristic peak	Observed peak
1.	N-H Stretch	3070-3350	3005.97
2.	O-H Stretch	3000-2500	2855.28
3.	C-H Stretch	2950 – 2850	2926.29
4.	C-CH ₃ Stretch	2862-2882, 2652-2972	2674.36

Screening of Oils, Surfactants and Co-surfactants for Microemulsion

To develop Microemulsion formulations for oral delivery of poorly water- soluble Dolutegravir, proper selection of oil is needed. The optimization of the components to be used in formulating Microemulsion was decided based on the solubility of Dolutegravir in the various oils, surfactants and co-surfactants.

The solubility of Dolutegravir amongst various oils investigated was found to be highest in oleic acid ($26.69 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg/ml}$), followed by castor oil and Eucalyptus oil. Amongst surfactant, Tween20 showed maximum solubility ($33.31 \pm 1.5 \text{ mg/ml}$) followed by Tween80. Ethanol showed highest solubility among the co-surfactants ($41.57 \pm 0.6 \text{ mg/ml}$), followed by PEG. Based on the solubility studies of Dolutegravir in oil, surfactant and cosurfactant and the preformulation studies we found Oleic acid, Tween20 and Ethanol could be the most appropriate combination for development of Microemulsion.

Solubility of Dolutegravir in various oils and surfactants

S. No	Excipients	Volume (ml)	Quantity (mg)	Solubility (mg/ml)
1	Water	5	100	0.41±1.8
2	Oleic acid	5	100	26.56±0.3
3	Castor oil	5	100	17.54±1.3
4	Olive oil	5	100	1.08±0.3
5	Eucalyptus oil	5	100	7.34±3.9
6	Coconut oil	5	100	0.97±0.1
7	Iso propyl myristate	5	100	0.85±0.3
8	Tween20	5	100	31.21±1.5
9	Tween80	5	100	32.27±1.8
10	Ethanol	5	100	41.36±0.6
11	PEG 400	5	100	22.05±0.9

% Solubility of Dolutegravir in different oils, Surfactants and Cosurfactants

Construction of pseudo-ternary phase diagrams and Microemulsion formulation

The Microemulsion existence region was determined by constructing phase diagrams. Fig.6.4.1 to 6.4.4 describes the pseudo ternary phase diagrams with various weight ratios of Tween20: Ethanol. The translucent region presented in phase diagram reveals the Microemulsion existence region. No distinct conversion from water-in oil (w/o) to oil-in-water (o/w) Microemulsion was observed. The rest of region on the phase diagram represents the turbid and conventional emulsions based on visual inspection. The phase study clearly revealed that Microemulsion existence region increased with increase in the weight ratio of surfactant (1 - 4). Four different proportions of oil, surfactant co –surfactant and water were selected for formulation.

Pseudo phase diagram containing surfactant and cosurfactant ratio 1:1

% OIL	% WATER	% S:CoS
7.35	66.18	26.47
13.79	55.17	31.04
20.98	48.95	30.07
26.67	40.00	33.33
32.26	32.26	35.48
42.86	28.57	28.57
40.00	17.14	42.86
50.00	12.50	37.50
69.23	7.69	23.08

Data for phase diagram of oleic acid/tween20/ethanol/water (1:1)

Pseudo phase diagram containing surfactant and co-surfactant ratio 1:2.

%Oil	% Water	% s:cos
6.81	61.22	31.97
12.13	48.48	39.39
16.21	37.84	45.95
21.39	32.09	46.52
26.31	26.32	47.37
11.10	22.22	44.44
40.00	17.14	42.86
47.06	11.76	41.18
56.25	6.25	37.50

Data for phase diagram of oleic acid/tween20/ethanol/water (1:2)

Pseudo phase diagram containing surfactant and co-surfactant ratio 2:1

%OIL	%WATER	%S:CoS
7.69	69.23	23.08
14.08	56.34	29.58
17.44	40.70	41.86
26.97	41.96	30.07
33.34	33.33	33.33
43.47	28.99	27.54
43.75	18.75	37.50
51.62	12.90	35.48
66.66	7.41	25.93

Data for phase diagram of oleic acid/tween20/ethanol/water 2:1

Pseudo phase diagram containing surfactant and cosurfactant ratio 4:1

% OIL	% WATER	% S:CoS
8.70	78.26	13.04
14.81	59.26	25.93
18.75	43.75	37.50
25.81	38.71	35.48
37.03	37.04	25.93
42.86	28.57	28.57
45.17	19.35	35.48
57.14	14.29	28.57

Data for phase diagram of oleic acid/tween20/ethanol/water 1:1

Evaluation of Physical Stability of Microemulsion Formulations Thermal stability and Centrifugation Studies on formulations

Microemulsions are thermodynamically stable system composed of fixed proportion of oil, surfactant/cosurfactant and water which does not tends to show any phase separation after the centrifugation. All formulation were seen free from physical instabilities.

Microemulsion formulations	Thermal stability			Centrifugation stability at 3000rpm
	Storage at 4°C	Storage at room temp.	Storage at 45°C	
DTR 1	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
DTR 2	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
DTR 3	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable
DTR 4	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable

Data for phase diagram of oleic acid/tween20/ethanol/water 1:1

Physicochemical evaluation of Microemulsion formulations Type of Microemulsion, Viscosity and pH of the formulation

Formulation code	pH	Viscosity	%Transmittance	Drug content
DTR 1	4.84±0.02	67.2±1.0 cps	89.08±0.4%	93.5±1.5%
DTR 2	4.82±0.02	63.7±2.2cps	91.13±0.8%	94.5±0.7%
DTR 3	4.84±0.02	56.8±1.0cps	93.52±0.6%	94.8±0.2%
DTR 4	4.86±0.02	55.9±1.1 cps	95.74±0.5%	96.3±0.6%

Physicochemical Parameters of developed Microemulsion

***In-vitro* drug release studies**

The plots of Cumulative percentage drug release V/s. Time, Cumulative percent drug V/s. Square root of Time and log Cumulative percent drug release in V/s. log Time were drawn and represented graphically as shown in Graph.6.7.1,6.7.2,6.7.3 respectively. The overall cumulative drug release for formulations DTR1, DTR2, DTR3 and DTR4 were found to be 65.72%, 62.66%, 76.21 and 86.88% respectively. Among all formulations DTR 4 shows highest drug release compared to other formulations.

Further these drug releases were subjected for mathematical treatment to check the mechanism of release.

The calculated values of various kinetic models are shown in table.

The values of diffusion coefficient (n) for formulations DTR1 to DTR4 are **0.8793**, **0.8594**, **0.8846** and **0.9056** respectively which indicates Anomalous mechanism. Korsmeyer Peppas's was found to be best fit model for all formulations.

Formulation code	Zero order	Higuchi model	Peppas's model		Mechanism
	r value	r value	r value	n value	
DTR 1	0.9703	0.9447	0.9957	0.8793	Anomalous
DTR 2	0.9722	0.9759	0.9910	0.8594	Anomalous
DTR 3	0.9724	0.9614	0.9900	0.8846	Anomalous
DTR 4	0.9702	0.9429	0.9875	0.9056	Anomalous

Curve fitting data of the release profile for Dolutegravir.

Comparative cumulative percent drug release versus time plots for formulations DTR 1-4.

Measurement of particle size and zeta potential

Globule size of Microemulsion was given in figure. Optimized Microemulsion showed particle size i.e., 54.3nm.

Zeta potential result of optimized Microemulsion was found to be -5.61mV

Average globule size of optimized Microemulsion.

Results	Mean (mV)	Area (%)	Width (mV)
Zeta Potential (mV): -5.61	Peak 1: -7.81	100.0	0.00
Zeta Deviation (mV): 83.1	Peak 2: 0.00	0.0	0.00
Conductivity (mS/cm): 0.00102	Peak 3: 0.00	0.0	0.00

Zeta potential of optimized formulation.

Stability studies

The studies revealed that there is slight reduction in the drug content and % transmittance after storage for 6months. Results were recorded in table. From the data it was indicated that the optimized Dolutegravir Microemulsion can be stable up to 6months. The studies revealed that there is slight reduction in the drug content and % transmittance after storage for 6months. Results were recorded in table.

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Temperature (°C)	Phase separation		% Transmittance		% of Assay	
	After 4months	After 6months	After 4months	After 6months	After 4months	After 6months
2-8 °C	No	No	95.08 ±0.8	94.87 ±1.3	95.23 ±0.2	94.30 ±0.1
Room temperature	No	No	95.72 ±1.2	94.48 ±1.5	94.23 ±0.4	93.60 ±1.1
Elevated temperature	No	No	95.22 ±1.2	93.80 ±0.6	94.00 ±0.7	93.28 ±0.3

Effect of temperature on stability of the optimized Microemulsion formulation (n=3, mean± SD)

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrates that the developed Microemulsion DTR 4 formulation containing oleic acid (27%), Tween20 (28%), Ethanol (7%) and water (3%) is a transparent, less viscous system and stable system. The Microemulsion systems exhibited a simple Newtonian flow. Results from *In vitro* studies revealed that developed DTR 4 possessed higher rate of drug release compared to the other formulations. This increased dissolution rate and increased solubility can ultimately lead to increase bioavailability of Dolutegravir. This study also demonstrated that physicochemical properties and *in-vitro* release were depended upon the contents of surfactant: cosurfactant, oil and water percentage in formulations. Phase diagrams indicated more width Microemulsion region with increase in surfactant ratio. It was confirmed that drug content of DTR 4 was more than the other formulations this may be because of increased solubility of drug in the oil. Particle size and Zeta potential of optimized formulation were found to be 54.30nm and -5.61Mv. The stability studies confirmed that the optimized formulation can stable up to 6months.

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